

METHODOLOGICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF THE APPLICATION OF STEAM EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGY IN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL CLASSES

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Abstract: This article discusses the importance of STEAM educational technology in primary education in teaching students to think creatively.

Keywords: Educational technology, modern education, integration, STEAM approach, creativity.

1 INTRODUCTION

As a result of the reforms carried out in our country in recent years, the demand for qualified personnel and mature specialists in all areas is further increasing. This in and of itself requires that our students have an interest in classes and that they increase their abilities in various subjects and that teachers' attention to education in every possible way is enhanced.

One of the ways to modernize and upgrade education in the world is to develop the STEAM education system. The main purpose of its implementation is to expand the capabilities of future primary education teachers by developing technical and Natural Science Education, based on the establishment of links between STEAM networks, taking into account the need to develop critical and creative thinking abilities of teachers and students.

2 Manuscript Preparation

STEAM education technology was first developed in America. Some education took note of graduates' careers and decided to combine subjects such as science, technology, engineering and mathematics, and this is how the STEM system was formed.

The STEAM International Assessment Program study examines students' skills in the following areas as well as subjects:

- (a) mature student knowledge in the Natural Sciences;
- (b) students' mastery of technology skills;
- (c) the students have the skills of construction and engineering and ingenuity;
- (g) students' understanding of art and creative competence;
- d) the fact that students have a high level of Mathematical Literacy.

Therefore, in the process of higher pedagogical education, it is advisable for students to master the basics of the formation of knowledge, skills and competencies on these grounds by teachers of the future primary class.

Remember that these routes are becoming the most popular in the modern world. Therefore, today the STEAM system is developing as one of the main trends. The application of the STEAM education direction and practical approach is also based on the integration of all five areas into a unified education system.

Its main idea is that practice is just as important as theoretical knowledge. That is, during learning, we need

to work not only with our brain, but also with our hand. Learning only on the walls of the class does not keep pace with the rapidly changing world. The main difference of the STEAM approach is that children use both the brain and their hands to successfully explore a wide variety of topics. They "absorb" the knowledge they receive.

If we say that the main purpose of traditional education is to teach knowledge and use this knowledge to think and create, the STEAM approach teaches us to combine the knowledge gained with real skills. This gives schoolchildren the opportunity not only to have some ideas, but also to put them into practice and implement them. Only knowledge that can be used in that reality is truly valuable.

The educator should try to make each lesson interesting. It is important to create opportunities for students so that they can tie each lesson to life and draw conclusions at the end of the lesson. It is necessary to connect with the school, because they will go to the threshold of this school tomorrow and give the children the knowledge they have gained. Now let's talk about ways to transition topics in natural science lessons based on the STEAM approach.

When applying STEAM technology in the teaching of "Natural Science", children understand nature, regularly study the world and thus learn their interests, engineering thinking, the ability to get out of critical situations, the basics of developing teamwork skills and leadership, self-expression, in turn, provide a fundamentally new level of children's development.

The letter S in STEAM technology indicates a fan. In this, students are introduced to theoretical information. In 2nd grade natural science, the Earth-planet theme is given. In the study of this topic, students receive practical training along with theoretical knowledge. Students make a model of the globe, The Sun. By doing this, they will have practical knowledge that the globe revolves around the sun while devising measures to overcome the global problems of the globe. On the basis of this topic, we can also reveal our abilities to know students, to think, to work independently, to be creative.

Theoretical information: the globe and its internal structure is the diameter of the globe – 12,800 km. The length of the equator, which is the length of the globe belt, is 40,000 km.

The letter T denotes technology. The data on the core, mantle, Earth's crust, Globe, North Pole, South Pole, equator are summarized and assigned to find answers to the following questions:

1. What is the diameter of the Earth and the length of its equator?
2. Explain the internal structure of the globe.
3. What is the temperature in the Earth's core?
4. What is a Globe, for what purpose is it used?
5. What do you know about the globe of berunius?

The letter E denotes engineering. Students are instructed to make a model of the Earth from paper and clay, plasticine.

The letter a denotes art. Readers write a poem, A Story, an essay based on the information given. In his notebooks, he is commissioned to draw a picture of the globe.

The letter M denotes mathematics. It will be necessary for them to calculate the axis of rotation of the globe, the North and south poles, and the dimensions of the equator from a mathematical point of view.

When passing topics about water in natural science lessons, we can approach it as follows. The theme of "pond", the first group of pond buoy is given the task of writing data, the second group of plasticine or colored paper is made without use, the third group is given the task of drawing, the fourth group, performing poetry songs, the fifth group is given the task of composing a mathematical problem.

Group 1: the watershed varies. A body of water is a source of slow flowing or non — flowing water that is formed by natural or artificial accumulation of water in natural or artificial low or deep areas of the Earth's surface, either in the absence of it, blocking the waterway and building a dam. The watershed is divided into permanent or seasonal (occurring in Leap Years) species. The permanent watershed includes oceans, seas, rivers, lakes, natural reservoirs, streams, ariks, etc. The seasonal catchment consists of artificial reservoirs, canals, ponds, etc. For example, on the territory of Uzbekistan, the Aral Sea, Amudarya, Syrdarya, Chirchiq rivers can be answered as a natural body of Water, The Tashkent Sea, the Chorvoq reservoir, the Andijan reservoir and other artificial bodies of water.

Group 2: living from plasticine.

Group 3: drawing.

Group 4: poetry, singing, Proverbs, saying riddles.

Poem: we give an example from the poems of Zahro

Hasanova

Water-dear boon
Daryomi u, soymi u,
Is it where the ditch passed.
Don't throw away every thing,
Do not gnaw at the ears.

Water-honesty, water-purity,
Tidiness and purity.
Water poison ne spaces,
Anhydrous growth spines.

Discharge cancellation,
Know, he has an Oval.
Drink honey, work, wedding,
Preserve the excess.

Proverb: Earth-treasure, water — gavhar.
Both water and water that spoil the Earth.

Hadith: whoever releases water where there is water is like a soul. Whoever releases water to a place where there is no water, it is as if he has revived a soul.

Riddle: there is a way on the surface of the water, there is a hand next to two.

Masala:the watershed is two times less than 30 meters wide. Find the surface of the pond.

The presentation of groups is combined and a general conclusion is drawn.

So we have the opportunity to implement science integration as well as STEAM technology by providing data based on the method of "creative labor", technology by making plasticine, engineering by drawing, art based on poetry, songs, and mathematics based on problem-making.

3 Conclusions

In conclusion, we would like to note that, compared to traditional teaching methods, the STEAM approach in high school encourages children to experiment, build models, independently create music and films, turn their ideas into reality and create a final product. This

educational approach allows children to effectively combine theory and practical skills, and facilitates university admission and further study.

REFERENCES:

- [1] Ergasheva G. B. The role of innovative pedagogical technologies in the development of Science and education in modern society //Scientific progress. – 2021.
- [2] Rajabova L. Advanced methods for solving mathematical problems based on the Steam education program // sentre nauchnix publikatsiy (Bukhdu. Face). – 2020. - t. 1. – №. 1.
- [3] Dilnoza Furqatovna Khalilova. (2023). Results that give an innovative educational environment in improving professional competence regarding the development of social relations in students. Conferencea
- [4] Makhmudov A. X., Abdurakhmanov Z. B. Achievements and challenges of using modern digital technologies in education //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2021. - T. 2. – №. CSPI conference
- [5] Akhmedova M.E (in co-authorship) pedagogical skill and professional competence of medical pedagogy. Educational-methodological manual T.: "Medical Publishing House LLC, 2021-62-63b.(126)
- [6] Akhmedova M.E. The module is the scientific and theoretical basis for creating independent assignments in the credit system (on the example of linguistic Sciences). Monograph. "Medical publishing house of Printing", LLC. Tashkent - 2022. 173 PP.
- [7] Akhmedova M. (in co –authorship) - pedagogy. Tutorial. T.; A science and technology publisher. 2018. — 393 b (102-b).
- [8] Akhmedova M.E.U.A.Tashkenbaeva., E.Suyunova general pedagogical theory and practice (textbook) – T.: Medical Press, 2022.